

Efficient Low-Power VLSI Design of a High-Speed Baugh-Wooley Multiplier Using Verilog HDL

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KEYWORDS

Portable Systems,
Low-Power Design,
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Baugh-Wooley Multiplier,
Verilog HDL.

ABSTRACT

The growing demand for portable systems and the necessity to reduce power consumption in ultra-high-density ULSI chips have driven rapid advancements in low-power design. Low-power optimization has become a critical concern in high-performance digital systems, including microprocessors, digital signal processing (DSP), and various computing applications. As portable computing and communication needs expand, power-efficient multipliers play a pivotal role in Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) system design. Multiplication is a fundamental operation in numerous DSP algorithms, necessitating the development of efficient multiplier architectures. This project focuses on the implementation of a high-speed, low-power multiplier using the shift-and-add method of the Baugh-Wooley multiplier. The study explores the design and implementation of Baugh-Wooley multipliers, emphasizing a Modified Baugh-Wooley architecture that achieves minimal area, power, and delay. The design is developed using Verilog HDL and simulated and synthesized using the Xilinx ISE tool.

1. INTRODUCTION

Baugh-Wooley (BW) multiplier, which provides physically packed together over the minimum area, low power consumption, and the high-speed unit, is called to be a good multiplier. The foremost steps for implementing a digital multiplier are generation of

partial product, reduction of partial product, and last addition [2]. In place of the multiplication of x-bit multiplicand and y-bit multiplier, a number of partial products are created, and the product formed is $x + y$ bits long.

The various types of multipliers in digital circuits are Booth multiplier, BW multiplier, Array multiplier, Sequential multiplier, Wallace tree multiplier, Combinational multiplier [2]. Both unsigned and signed operands can be used in multiplication so that a multiplier should serve this operation without any errors. The BW multiplier satisfies and uses 2's complement number system for the operation [2]. As work demonstrated in [3], a new multiplier design architecture technique for BW multiplier is proposed called as the reduction tree technique. It is a high performance technique which is used to minimize the generated partial products. A BW multiplier can be implemented to enhance the performance using technique to minimize the generated partial products. A BW multiplier can be implemented by using shift and add method to gain high speed with low power as proposed in [4]. This paper also represents BW multiplier design and implementation in Cadence (encounter) RTL compiler. In BW multiplier, the negative signs are moved to the last stages to maximize the regularity provided by the multiplication array by arranging the partial products. It produces a quite standard cell shape for manufacturing ease while sustaining good driving features. Each full adder within the multiplier performs a similar number of computations. This includes the crosswise ripple carry propagating the input signal a constant and a similar number of times [5]. As work proposed in [6], the modified BW architecture is proposed. A BW multiplier technique deals with two's complement representation of signed multiplicands for multiplication. Reduction of latency and area can be achieved by Wallace tree multiplier architecture as proposed in [7] by using the compressors. Significant work on the design of BW with a new reversible 5×5 multiplier is explored which will also concentrate on the reversible computing field is proposed in [7, 8]. A reversible circuit brings the input back from the output with a one-to-one input-output unique relationship. This leads to equal the number of inputs and outputs. Hence, a cell useful in designing BW multiplier is proposed. The scenario in [8], motivates the study of the reversible computing field in which circuit will bring back the inputs from the outputs. In numerous research areas like low power CMOS design, DNA computing, quantum computing and nanotechnology reversible logic is applied frequently. The BW

multiplication algorithm is ideal for recursive multiplication in digital signal processing applications. In addition to this algorithm, decomposition sense can be used to increase the multiplication speed and reduce the path delay. By combining this decomposition logic to the BW algorithm, a high speed multiplier is designed and implemented in [9]. Various new techniques are discussed to increase multiplication speed as discussed in work [10]. Several changes have also been carried out for BW, Wallace tree and Booth algorithms. A fixed width, parallel multiplier had been designed and it truncated eight least significant columns of the partial product array [11]. The implementation of 4-bit and 8-bit multipliers along with the comparison analysis of Array, Wallace, and BW multiplier types are presented in [12]. The multipliers are implemented and designs are compared both on FPGA and ASIC in 90 nm. The motivation to study the BW multiplier is that, it consumes the least area for both the ASIC and FPGA implementation. In this paper, an 8-bit signed BW multiplier is designed and implemented along with the RTL to GDSII flow. RTL file is generated using the Verilog code of BW multiplier. The VSD flow is used to transform RTL into the GDSII file along with the several intermediate steps. Implementation of BW multiplier on 45 nm technology has been done in cadence. The results like area, power and delay are compared for 180 nm and 45 nm, and also with Booth multiplier.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Low-Power 8-Bit Baugh–Wooley Multiplier Based on Wallace Tree Architecture (X. Xiong and M. Lin):

This study presents the design and simulation of an 8-bit Baugh–Wooley multiplier utilizing Wallace tree architecture for efficient signed multiplication in two's complement representation. The Wallace tree approach minimizes delay by combining partial products at the earliest possible stage, significantly improving speed. Additionally, the integration of carry-save adders (CSA) reduces the number of addition cycles, further enhancing computational efficiency. The multiplier was designed and simulated using PSPICE, and results demonstrated that the Wallace tree architecture outperformed the conventional array structure in terms of both speed and power efficiency.

Design and Performance of Baugh–Wooley Multiplier Using Carry Look-Ahead Adder (T. Janani and R. N. Kumar)

With power dissipation being a key challenge in VLSI design, this work compares low-power multipliers using different adder architectures. The study explores the design and implementation of a 16-bit Baugh–Wooley multiplier employing the shift-and-add technique, which optimizes computation by reducing the number of adders and iterative steps. This approach results in a smaller chip footprint, crucial for high-performance computing applications. Comparative analysis of power, delay, and area footprint was conducted using Cadence RTL Compiler with 180nm process technology, demonstrating the effectiveness of carry look-ahead adders in reducing power consumption.

Design and Implementation of High-Speed Baugh–Wooley and Modified Booth Multiplier Using Cadence RTL (J. Antony and JyotirmoyPathak)

This research examines the performance of Baugh–Wooley and Modified Booth multipliers, which are widely used for signed multiplication. While the Modified Booth Multiplier is typically favored for its speed, the Baugh–Wooley multiplier is often overlooked due to its complex structure. The study implements 8-bit multipliers using both conventional methods and the High-Performance Multiplier Reduction Tree (HPM) technique. Comparative analysis using Cadence 180nm RTL Compiler revealed that Baugh–Wooley multipliers, when optimized with reduction tree techniques, can surpass the speed of Modified Booth multipliers while maintaining a smaller area footprint.

Design of Baugh–Wooley and Wallace Tree Multiplier Using Two-Phase Clocked Adiabatic Static CMOS Logic (V. S. Muley, A. Tom, and T. Vigneswaran)

This paper explores low-power Baugh–Wooley and Wallace tree multipliers implemented using two-phase clocked adiabatic static CMOS logic (2PASCL). The study compares the power consumption of these designs against conventional static CMOS logic implementations. The multipliers were designed using 45nm CMOS technology, and results indicated that the Wallace tree multiplier exhibited 62.66% lower power consumption compared to the Baugh–Wooley multiplier under static CMOS logic conditions, making it a more power-efficient alternative for VLSI applications.

High-Performance Baugh–Wooley Multiplier Using Carry Skip Adder Structure (R. A. Sekar and B. Gopinath)

This study explores the Baugh–Wooley algorithm for high-speed multiplication in digital signal processing (DSP) applications. By implementing decomposition logic, the critical path delay was significantly reduced, enhancing overall speed. The performance of the Baugh–Wooley multiplier was compared with Vedic and Modified Booth multipliers, showing improvements in delay, power dissipation, and area efficiency. The design was implemented using FPGA-based architecture in Xilinx 12.3, and results demonstrated that Baugh–Wooley multipliers outperform Vedic and Modified Booth multipliers in terms of power, delay, and area efficiency due to the reduced number of partial products.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The algorithm of Baugh–Wooley multiplier is a simple method of implementing digitally signed data multiplications. Baugh–Wooley array multipliers multiply signed numbers in 2’s complement data representation. The partial product bits have been reorganized, as depicted in Figure 1 where the 8-bit multiplication algorithm is described. A bit “1” is added in the 8th column by setting S8 as bit “1” from the carry-in of the full adder. Figure 2 shows the operation of the multiplier where X and Y are 8-bit multiplicand and multiplier respectively. Here, P is the partial product of the particular multiplication i.e. X_i and Y_j will give P_{ij} and S (16-bit) is the final product of $X \times Y$. An 8x8 bit BW multiplier can be designed with the help of partial product array by following these steps:

- i. The most significant bit (MSB) of the first N-1 partial product rows are inverted (Here N = 8).
- ii. All bits of the last partial-product row, except its MSB, are inverted.
- iii. Add Bit ‘1’ to the 8th column.
- iv. Invert the MSB of the last result

Figure 1: Process of 8-bit multiplication

The final answer of the multiplication can be produced by subtraction of the absolute two positive terms and the first two terms. In the process, instead of subtraction operation, the 2's complement of the last two expressions is obtained along with adding all terms, which will give the final product. The number of bits in the last two terms is (n-1), where each bit expands from 2n-1 to 22n-3 binary weights. Whereas, the final multiplied answer is 2n-bit and it extends from 20 to 22n-1 binary weight. Firstly, zero paddings are necessary for every last two terms consisting of the P (product) equation for adding other terms as a 2n-bit number. Then these padded terms are continued from 20 to 22n-1 binary weight.

Figure 2: Algorithm of 8-bit BW Multiplier with partial product method.

By using a two-input AND gate, the partial product bits can be calculated for every operand bit. A two-input NAND gate is being used instead of an AND gate for several partial product bits functional blocks. This will make the general block diagram of the 8-bit BW multiplier along with the array structure of 8x8 bit functional blocks

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Simulation Result of Multiplier

Figure 3: Simulation Result of Multiplier

Here we can give the inputs as A=6, B=3, then the final output is 18.

Block Diagram of Multiplier

Figure 4: Block diagram of Multiplier

RTL Schematic

Figure 5: Internal diagram of RTL schematic

Estimation of Power

Figure 6: Estimation of power

Figure 6 estimates power using approximate multiplier and it is 0.226W.

Estimation of Delay

Figure 7: Estimation of Delay

Figure 7 estimates delay of approximate multiplier and it is 30.11ns.

Estimation of Area

Figure 8: Estimation of Area

5.CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this project addresses the critical need for low-power, high-performance multipliers in the context of portable systems and ultra-high-density VLSI chips. With the growing demand for power-efficient designs in digital systems, particularly in microprocessors and DSP applications, the proposed high-speed, low-power multiplier based on the shift-and-add method of the Baugh-Wooley multiplier provides a valuable solution. By focusing on a Modified Baugh-Wooley architecture, the design achieves significant optimizations in area, power consumption, and delay, making it suitable for modern VLSI system design. The implementation using Verilog HDL and the simulation and synthesis through the Xilinx ISE tool demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed approach, contributing to the advancement of efficient multiplier architectures for a range of computational applications.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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